

ВЛИЯНИЕ КИСЛОРОДНОЙ ТЕРАПИИ НА ОТЕК МОЗГА ПРИ ОСТРОМ ИШЕМИЧЕСКОМ ИНСУЛЬТЕ: ОБЗОР ЛИТЕРАТУРЫ**Жумагали Д.Ш.**<https://orcid.org/0009-0009-6435-7416>**Сыздыкбаев М.К.**<https://orcid.org/0000-0002-0561-4111>*НАО «Медицинский университет Семей»,
г. Семей, Республика Казахстан***EFFECTS OF OXYGEN THERAPY ON BRAIN EDEMA DURING ACUTE ISCHEMIC STROKE: A SCOPING REVIEW****Zhumagali D.***1st year student of Master program in Medicine,*<https://orcid.org/0009-0009-6435-7416>**Syzdykbayev M.**<https://orcid.org/0000-0002-0561-4111>*NCJSC "Semey Medical University"**Semey, Republic of Kazakhstan***Аннотация**

Отек мозга является одним из наиболее тяжелых осложнений острого ишемического инсульта (ОИИ), значительно ухудшающим прогноз для пациента и затрудняющим восстановление нейронных функций. По данным Министерства здравоохранения Республики Казахстан, ежегодно в стране регистрируется около 40 тысяч случаев инсультов, из которых примерно 80% составляют ишемические инсульты. Около 60% пациентов, перенесших инсульт, становятся инвалидами. 5 тыс. человек погибают в течение первых 10 дней заболевания. Около 70% пациентов, перенесших инсульт, нуждаются в дополнительной помощи. Исследования таких авторов как Zheng Ding, Wesley C. Tong «Hyperbaric Oxygen Therapy in Acute Ischemic Stroke: A Review» и Blaise Cozene, Nadia Sadanandan «An Extra Breath of Fresh Air: Hyperbaric Oxygenation as a Stroke Therapeutic» указывают на положительное влияние гипербарической кислородотерапии на уменьшение объема отека мозга и снижение нейрональных повреждений. Однако результаты этих исследований неоднозначны, и до сих пор не существует единого мнения о её эффективности и оптимальных режимах применения.

Цель исследования

Цель данного исследования – проанализировать существующие данные о влиянии кислородотерапии на отек мозга у пациентов с острым ишемическим инсультом (ОИИ) на основе литературных источников. Необходимо решить следующие задачи: 1) изучить современные представления о механизмах формирования отека мозга при ОИИ; 2) проанализировать эффективность гипербарической кислородотерапии как метода лечения.

Методы

Методом исследования является обзор существующей литературы, посвященной влиянию кислородотерапии на отек мозга при остром ишемическом инсульте. Для этого был проведен анализ научных публикаций, включая статьи в медицинских журналах, монографии и отчеты о клинических исследованиях, доступных в международных и отечественных базах данных.

Результаты

Результаты проведенного обзора литературы показывают, что использование кислородотерапии, особенно гипербарической, демонстрирует потенциал в снижении отека мозга у пациентов с острым ишемическим инсультом.

Выводы

Результаты исследования позволяют сделать вывод, что, хотя кислородотерапия, особенно гипербарическая, действительно может снижать объем отека и уменьшать нейрональные повреждения, результаты остаются противоречивыми. Основные различия в данных могут быть связаны с различиями в методиках, времени начала терапии и характеристиках пациентов.

Abstract

Cerebral edema is one of the most severe complications of acute ischemic stroke (AIS), significantly worsening the prognosis for the patient and complicating the recovery of neuronal functions. According to the Ministry of Health of the Republic of Kazakhstan, approximately 40,000 cases of stroke are registered in the country each year, of which about 80% are ischemic strokes. About 60% of stroke survivors become disabled. Five thousand people die within the first 10 days of the illness. Approximately 70% of stroke patients require assistance. Research by authors such as Zheng Ding and Wesley C. Tong in "Hyperbaric Oxygen Therapy in Acute Ischemic Stroke: A Review" and Blaise Cozene and Nadia Sadanandan in "An Extra Breath of Fresh Air: Hyperbaric Oxygenation

as a Stroke Therapeutic” indicates the positive impact of hyperbaric oxygen therapy on reducing brain edema and decreasing neuronal damage. However, the results of these studies are inconsistent, and there is still no consensus on its effectiveness and optimal application protocols.

Objective of the Study

The aim of this study is to analyze the existing data on the impact of oxygen therapy on brain edema in patients with acute ischemic stroke (AIS) based on literature sources. The following tasks need to be addressed: 1) to study current views on the mechanisms of brain edema formation in AIS; 2) to analyze the effectiveness of hyperbaric oxygen therapy as a treatment method.

Methods

The research method is a review of the existing literature dedicated to the impact of oxygen therapy on brain edema in acute ischemic stroke. This involved an analysis of scientific publications, including articles in medical journals, monographs, and reports on clinical studies available in international and domestic databases.

Results

The results of the literature review indicate that the use of oxygen therapy, especially hyperbaric oxygen therapy, demonstrates potential in reducing brain edema in patients with acute ischemic stroke.

Conclusions

The results of the study suggest that while oxygen therapy, particularly hyperbaric oxygen therapy, can indeed reduce the volume of edema and decrease neuronal damage, the results remain contradictory. The main differences in the data may be associated with variations in methodologies, the timing of therapy initiation, and patient characteristics.

Ключевые слова: кислородотерапия, отек мозга, острый ишемический инсульт, гипербарическая оксигенация, гипоксия мозга, нейропротекция.

Keywords: oxygen therapy, brain edema, acute ischemic stroke, hyperbaric oxygenation, brain hypoxia, neuroprotection.

A stroke can be defined as a sudden neurological deficit of presumed vascular origin [4, 5, 8]. It is both a leading cause of mortality worldwide and a primary cause of disability. Approximately one-third of survivors require significant assistance in daily life within a year after the event.

Researchers generally categorize stroke into two major subgroups: ischemic (disruption of blood flow) and hemorrhagic (bleeding in the brain), with the former accounting for 73% to 86% of all cases [19, 29]. Studies show that, on average, ischemic stroke has a lower fatality rate than hemorrhagic stroke (23% vs. 62% over one year), and treatment differs for the two subgroups. Therefore, early and accurate diagnosis is essential. Since clinical assessment is unreliable for determining the type of stroke, neuroimaging (preferably using computed tomography (CT)) is required for optimal treatment [9, 11, 16, 25].

According to S. Blaise, during cerebral ischemic stroke, neural tissue suffers from hypoxia. As hypoxia persists, neurons lose their ability to maintain ion homeostasis. Oxygen free radicals accumulate, damaging cell membranes, and irreversible changes lead to inevitable cell death [11]. These changes may occur rapidly, even before therapy is initiated, but in some individuals, symptoms worsen gradually or in stages over several hours or days [6]. This observation suggests that careful management of hemodynamic, respiratory, and metabolic factors aimed at maintaining oxygenation could be beneficial. Indeed, intensive stroke management protocols and antiplatelet therapy have been shown to positively influence outcomes [22, 31].

According to researchers such as V.S. Zhou, L.J. Liu, and B. Liu, cerebral edema is a condition in which excessive fluid accumulates in the brain tissues [24]. This accumulation can be caused by disruption of the blood-brain barrier, which normally prevents various

substances from entering the brain from the bloodstream [10]. When this barrier is damaged or when cell membranes break down, the exchange of substances and fluids between the circulatory system and brain tissues is disrupted. In such cases, fluid enters brain cells and the intercellular space, leading to the development of edema [11].

The primary mechanism of cerebral edema formation is an increase in fluid volume within cells (cytotoxic edema) or in the intercellular space (vasogenic edema) [6]. This process leads to increased intracranial pressure, which compresses surrounding tissues and impairs circulation. Since the skull provides a limited space, any increase in tissue volume results in serious consequences, including the displacement of brain structures. This extremely dangerous condition requires immediate medical intervention [17].

According to recent studies, cerebral edema following a stroke is one of the most frequent and severe complications [23]. Statistics show that approximately one in three stroke patients develops cerebral edema, which can significantly worsen the prognosis [19]. Due to disrupted circulation and oxygen deprivation in affected brain regions, irreversible cell damage may occur, increasing the risk of mortality [14].

N.V. Pizova, in her study "Issues of Rehabilitation of Patients After Stroke in Outpatient Settings," highlights the critical importance of timely diagnosis and treatment of cerebral edema following a stroke, emphasizing that its significance cannot be overstated [8]. Rapid medical intervention can save the patient's life and prevent further complications. Treatment includes drug therapy aimed at reducing intracranial pressure, and in severe cases, surgical intervention may be necessary, such as removing part of the skull to reduce pressure on the brain tissues [22].

Cerebral edema, therefore, is a dangerous complication that significantly worsens the patient's condition

and requires urgent treatment. Prompt measures can greatly reduce the risk of severe consequences, including fatal outcomes.

According to N.S. Pan, C.S. Chin, and D.Y. Yang, hyperbaric oxygen therapy (HBOT) is an additional treatment method proposed for patients with ischemic stroke [19]. HBOT involves delivering 100% oxygen at an ambient pressure exceeding 1.0 absolute atmosphere (ATA). The therapy is conducted in a special sealed chamber where the pressure is increased, allowing the patient to breathe pure oxygen, which significantly raises its partial pressure in the body's tissues [21].

D. Zheng, in his study «*Hyperbaric Oxygen Therapy in Acute Ischemic Stroke: A Review*», notes that the HBOT procedure typically involves increasing the pressure to 1.5–3.0 ATA, allowing oxygen to dissolve more effectively in the blood and reach areas affected by ischemia [27]. This improves oxygenation in brain tissues experiencing oxygen deficits, reducing hypoxic damage and promoting neuronal recovery [18].

According to V.A. Predko's research «*Use of Oxygen in Medicine*», the duration of HBOT sessions ranges from 60 to 120 minutes, and they may be conducted one or two times daily, depending on the patient's condition [7]. The primary advantage of HBOT is its ability to deliver higher oxygen levels to critically deprived areas, which may accelerate stroke recovery. However, despite promising results, the effectiveness of HBOT remains a topic of discussion, requiring further research to determine its optimal clinical use [31].

According to studies by XG Zhang, ZL Jiang, and GH Wang, hyperbaric oxygen therapy (HBOT) serves as a potential non-invasive treatment in which pure oxygen is administered in a sealed chamber under high atmospheric pressure [26]. With increased oxygenation, HBOT can improve oxygen flow from the lungs to systemic organs and may reduce secondary effects of brain damage, including the initiation of apoptotic pathways, oxidative stress, and excessive inflammation [29]. It has been shown that by restoring oxygen tension, HBOT helps restore cellular energy production, stabilize intracellular calcium, reduce NOX expression, and mitigate oxidative stress [15].

The mechanisms achieved through HBOT can also be realized at lower or normal oxygen concentrations. During recovery, as oxygen levels return to normal, an increase in HIF-1 α synthesis occurs, creating a "relatively hypoxic environment." This environment activates matrix metalloproteinases (MMPs) and stimulates the synthesis of erythropoietin (EPO), which is also observed in healthy individuals. A. Varvinsky argues that HBOT mechanisms can be triggered even at low oxygen levels [1].

HBOT has demonstrated efficacy in treating various neurological disorders, including head trauma, paralysis, and strokes. Although there are currently insufficient therapeutic methods for many neurological diseases, HBOT research shows promising results. The primary goal of using HBOT is to reduce the effects of ischemic stroke and improve patients' quality of life [19].

The next section will review studies highlighting the application of HBOT for ischemic stroke treatment,

focusing on post-stroke preconditioning and the use of HBOT in stem cell transplantation. Preclinical data supporting the effectiveness of HBOT in the context of stroke will also be presented [11, 17, 25, 28, 30].

In the study by BC Zhou, LJ Liu, and B. Liu, it is noted that hyperbaric oxygen therapy (HBOT) can provide numerous positive effects, such as accelerated oxygen delivery to tissues [24]. This is particularly crucial in cases of acute ischemic stroke, where certain areas of the brain suffer from oxygen deprivation and edema. Increasing oxygen levels in the cells can help activate metabolic processes and improve the patient's overall condition, thereby slowing the progression of neurodegenerative processes [23].

Hyperoxia, which occurs due to HBOT, has unique effects, including: 1) reducing lipid peroxidation; 2) decreasing leukocyte activity; and 3) restoring the integrity of the blood-brain barrier [30]. These factors help protect damaged brain areas and prevent further neuronal damage, especially in the ischemic penumbra, where cells retain moderate viability. Additionally, HBOT helps regulate cellular metabolism and control inflammatory processes, thereby protecting neural cells [14].

However, hyperoxygenation can also have some drawbacks. Excessive oxygen levels may contribute to oxidative stress, leading to an increase in free radicals [6]. These active molecules can damage cell membranes, degrade protein structures, and negatively affect DNA, ultimately worsening the patient's condition. Special attention must be given to the brain, as neurons are particularly vulnerable to changes in metabolic reactions [22].

HBOT may not always be effective and can even be potentially harmful. For instance, in stroke patients, it could lead to serious consequences, especially in the presence of comorbid vascular conditions. Therefore, to reduce the risk of complications, the use of HBOT in such patients requires thorough monitoring [6, 7, 8].

HBOT offers potential advantages in treating ischemic stroke; however, the risks associated with oxidative stress necessitate a cautious approach. More research is needed to accurately define optimal therapy parameters, aiming to minimize harm and enhance therapeutic benefits [18].

HBOT therapy carries some risks of side effects, including damage to the ears, sinuses, and lungs due to pressure, temporary worsening of nearsightedness, claustrophobia, and oxygen toxicity. While serious side effects are rare, HBOT cannot be considered entirely harmless.

X. Pan emphasizes that mitochondrial dysfunctions are crucial elements in stroke treatment according to recent studies [20]. Mitochondria are essential in clinical practice and neurobiology, providing the metabolic activity necessary for neuronal survival, protection against widespread cellular self-destruction (apoptosis), and functioning under catastrophic hypoxic conditions [19].

Among diseases contributing to stroke production, hypertension, atherosclerosis, and diabetes are the most prevalent, particularly in elderly individuals with mitochondrial dysfunction [14].

Reactive oxygen species (ROS) are produced in mitochondria and can damage mitochondrial DNA. Excessive amounts of these oxygen species disrupt normal mitochondrial function, contributing to stress under hypoxic or hyperoxic conditions [27].

Clinical tests, based on in-depth scientific analysis, have led to a novel stroke treatment method called Normoxic Therapeutic Compression (NTC). NTC combines the benefits of hyperbaric chambers with antioxidants, which activate electron transfer in the mitochondrial respiratory chain [31].

Researchers highlight that stroke therapy aimed at restoring cellular respiration and oxygen normalization differs from traditional barotherapy. This method reduces the formation of free radicals and restores lipid peroxidation processes. Clinical trials have demonstrated its effectiveness in recovering cellular respiration and improving cerebral blood flow in ischemic areas for both ischemic and hemorrhagic strokes. The method also boosts ATP molecule synthesis and helps dissolve carbon dioxide, optimizing metabolism in the central nervous system and regulating carbon dioxide balance in the blood, which is vital for oxygen delivery to brain cells [19].

D. Zheng, in the study *"Hyperbaric Oxygen Therapy in Acute Ischemic Stroke: A Review"*, notes that external environmental factors influence metabolism. The reason lies in the fact that tissue respiration is based on redox reactions, and oxygen and carbon dioxide present in liquid media play a key role in this chain of processes [27].

Under increased pressure at constant temperature and volume, the metabolic processes of the body are significantly activated. The increase in pressure leads to enhanced aerobic biochemical reactions, which promotes a more intense formation of adenosine triphosphate (ATP), carbon dioxide (CO₂), and water (H₂O). This helps maintain the energy balance of cells and contributes to the restoration of damaged tissues, which is especially important in conditions of oxygen deficiency, such as in the case of a stroke [27].

The best results are achieved when the pressure is increased by 50-100 mmHg compared to atmospheric pressure, leading to effective metabolic processes and optimal oxygen supply to the cells. When the oxygen level exceeds 2%, the saturation of tissues with oxygen improves, hypoxia decreases, and restorative processes are activated [23, 28].

When the level of carbon dioxide exceeds the established norm, the concentration of this gas in the body and in exhaled air begins to fall [11]. This can disrupt normal gas exchange and have a suppressive effect on metabolism. A decrease in CO₂ concentration leads to a slowing of redox reactions, which directly affects the activity of cellular processes and can cause hypocapnia [3].

In the context of hyperbaric oxygen therapy, changes in metabolism are very important. Even minor fluctuations in gas concentrations can significantly affect the patient's well-being. This is why continuous monitoring of pressure and oxygen levels is critically important to prevent adverse effects and ensure normal metabolism.

It should be noted that therapy involving increased pressure, tolerated by patients, can lead to changes in metabolism, specifically an increase in carbon dioxide levels in the blood and a decrease in oxygen. Achieving and maintaining optimal levels of oxygen and carbon dioxide in the blood are key aspects for safe and effective therapy under increased pressure.

D. Page, in the study "Emergency department hypoxia is associated with increased mortality in mechanically ventilated patients: a cohort study," notes that the combination of normal pressure therapy (NPT) with antioxidants provides an opportunity to effectively reduce oxidative stress due to more active electron transport on mitochondrial membranes [31]. The application of NPT improves the pO₂ level in the blood and enhances treatment efficacy compared to standard oxygen procedures. Additionally, restoring the balance of lipid peroxidation in cells significantly amplifies the positive effects of subsequent therapies [18].

Numerous studies have shown that optimal oxygen therapy requires appropriate pressure, which promotes optimal oxygen saturation and activates cellular metabolism [3, 11, 16, 18, 19]. However, excessive pressure can negatively affect heart function and lead to serious consequences, such as dysfunction of the heart muscle, overload, exhaustion of muscle fibers, and discomfort in patients with severe illnesses. For this reason, NPT, being an experimentally studied method, is considered safer and more effective than traditional oxygen therapy regimens and hyperbaric oxygen therapy (HBOT) for treating reduced cerebral blood flow [5].

In experiments with rats, a barochamber was used where, at 1.2 ATA and after 20 minutes under pressure, it was possible to restore neuronal cells following a stroke. Y.P. Orlov describes a study in which neuronal cells were preserved in 80% of the tested rats after a 14-hour delay and 15 minutes under pressure. The effectiveness of the barochamber application was recorded the next day, while in the control group, only 50% of the cells survived, typically with reduced size [5].

Oxygen therapy plays a key role in the recovery of patients after a stroke. Studies show its effectiveness in improving lost bodily functions [1]. A stroke often leads to significant circulatory disturbances, which can negatively impact the functioning of the respiratory and excretory systems, including the lungs, liver, and kidneys, increasing the risk of disseminated intravascular coagulation (DIC). Normal pressure therapy (NPT) helps restore the functioning of these organs, enhances metabolic processes, and reduces the likelihood of cystic complications, thereby increasing the chances of successful recovery [3].

Due to oxygen therapy, there is an improvement in microcirculation in the organs, which contributes to enhanced therapeutic efficacy. In combination with antibacterial agents, hormones, and glycosides, it reduces the toxic effects of the aforementioned medications [16].

Oxygen therapy facilitates the restoration of brain activity after a stroke by eliminating the primary negative factor—oxygen deficiency in the tissues. Due to

premature cessation of blood circulation during ischemia, mass neuron death may occur. The application of oxygen restores this disruption, leading to improved cellular metabolism and oxygen levels in brain tissues [21].

The foundation of scientifically grounded atherotherapy measures should be considered the restoration of oxygen exchange and the enhancement of its presence in the blood against the backdrop of brain activity [7]. The use of oxygen in large quantities (such as hyperbaric oxygen therapy) creates an environment for increased oxygenation of the pulmonary arteries, which raises the oxygen content in hemoglobin and optimizes blood circulation. This contributes to improved metabolism and prevents further damage to brain neurons [13].

The primary goal of oxygen therapy is to enhance microcirculation. As a result, it reduces brain swelling, which in turn decreases pressure on blood vessels and neurons. This technique protects cells from further damage and maintains their viability in areas with oxygen deficiency. There is also a positive effect on the entire circulatory system [14].

Oxygen therapy is a method suitable for different types of strokes, whether ischemic or hemorrhagic [22]. It is effective in both acute cases and during the recovery period, and it can be applied to patients with comorbid cardiovascular diseases. This makes oxygen therapy a universal solution in the rehabilitation process [15].

Thus, the method known as oxygen therapy represents a safe and highly effective way to combat strokes. It aims to restore microcirculation and normalize metabolism in the affected area, allowing it to surpass outdated oxygen therapies associated with free radical oxidative processes in terms of efficacy. The research on oxygen therapy is based on extensive scientific data, and this method has no contraindications, significantly reducing the mortality rate in the acute stages of both ischemic and hemorrhagic strokes.

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